

GOODS AND SERVICES TAX COUNCIL (GSTC) AND POLITICAL TRANSFORMATION

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I. INTRODUCTION

The GST is the largest-ever tax reform in the fiscal history of India. It charts a new course for fiscal federalism in India that focuses on cooperation instead of self-interests. The spirit of cooperative federalism requires both the Union and the State governments to sacrifice their fiscal autonomy in favor of a collective decision-making process. The giving up of the fiscal autonomy is unprecedented and reflects that the modern economy of today calls for increasing cooperation among the economic players for the common good, instead of focusing on individual gains.

The current taxation system in India provides truncated taxation powers to the central government (the Centre) and the States and is not in tune with the modern businesses and the complex supply chains. The patchwork of taxes has led to balkanization of the common market and fragmentation of the supply chains.

The differential taxes in different States give rise to arbitrage opportunities. Taxes such as central sales tax (an origin-based tax) and entry tax being non-creditable further add to the costs of businesses.

To add to the woes, India has approximately 600 check posts. Goods carriage vehicles in India barely travel 280 km per day against a world average of 400 km per day. The World Bank has observed that 60% of truck drivers' time is spent off-road, negotiating at check posts and at toll plazas.

The GST overcomes these gaps. While the States will get the power to tax both goods and

services, the Centre will be able to levy taxes beyond the manufacturing point, across the full supply chain. At the same time, the tax provisions that restricted inter-State movement of goods within the country will now be dispensed with. These provisions are absolutely fundamental to modernizing the tax system and making it simple and efficient.

Goods and Services Tax (GST)

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is an indirect tax which was introduced in India on 1 July 2017 and was applicable throughout India which replaced multiple cascading taxes levied by the central and state governments. The GST is a Value added Tax (VAT) is a comprehensive indirect tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods as well as services at the national level. It replace all indirect taxes levied on goods and services by the Indian Central and state governments. It is aimed at being comprehensive for most goods and services. It was introduced as The Constitution (One Hundred and First Amendment) Act 2017, following the passage of Constitution 122nd Amendment Act Bill. The GST is governed by a GST Council and its Chairman is the Finance Minister of India.

The introduction of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a very significant step in the field of indirect tax reforms in India. By amalgamating a large number of Central and State taxes into a single tax, GST will mitigate ill effects of cascading or double taxation in a major way and pave the way for a common national market. It also imply that the actual burden of indirect taxes on

goods and services would be much more transparent to the consumer. Introduction of GST also make Indian products competitive in the domestic and international markets owing to the full neutralization of input taxes across the value chain of production and distribution. Last but not the least, this tax, because of its transparent and self-policing character, is easier to administer. It also encourage a shift from the informal to formal economy.

GST and Centre-State Financial Relations

Currently, fiscal powers between the Centre and the States are clearly demarcated in the Constitution with almost no overlap between the respective domains. The Centre has the powers to levy tax on the manufacture of goods (except alcoholic liquor for human consumption, opium, narcotics etc.) while the States have the powers to levy tax on sale of goods. In case of inter-states sales, the Centre has the powers to levy a tax (the Central Sales Tax) but, the tax is collected and retained entirely by the originating States. As for services, it is the Centre alone that is empowered to levy Service Tax. Since the States are not empowered to levy any tax on the sale or purchase of goods in the course of their importation into or exportations from India, the Centre levies and collects this tax in addition to the Basic Customs Duty. This additional duty of customs (commonly known as CVD and SAD) counter balance excise duty, sales tax, State VAT and other taxes levied on the like domestic product. Introduction of GST required amendments in the Constitution so as to empower the Centre and the States concurrently to levy and collect GST.

The assignment of concurrent jurisdiction to the Centre and the States for the levy of GST required a unique institutional mechanism that would ensure that decisions about the structure,

design and operation of GST are taken jointly by the two.

To address all these and other issues, the Constitution (122nd Amendment) Bill was introduced in the 16th Lok Sabha on 19.12.2014. The Bill provides for a levy of GST on supply of all goods or services except alcohol for human consumption. The tax shall be levied as Dual GST separately, but concurrently the Union (CGST) and the States (SGST). The Parliament would have exclusive power to levy GST (IGST) on inter state trade or commerce (including imports) in goods and services. The Central Government will have the power to levy excise duty in addition to GST, on tobacco and tobacco products.

The Constitution (One Hundred and Twenty-Second Amendment) Bill, 2014 was introduced in the Lok Sabha on 19 December 2014, and passed by the House on 6 May 2015. In the Rajya Sabha, the bill was referred to a Select Committee on 14 May 2015. The Select Committee of the Rajya Sabha submitted its report on the bill on 22 July 2015. The bill was passed by the Rajya Sabha on 3 August 2016, and the amended bill was passed by the Lok Sabha on 8 August 2016.

The bill, after ratification by the States, received assent from President of India on 8 September 2016, and was notified in The Gazette of India on the same date. The GST Council has also been notified w.e.f. 12th September, 2016. GST Council is being assisted by a Secretariat.

GST Council

As per Article 279A (1) of the amended Constitution, the GST Council has to be constituted by the President within 60 days of the commencement of Article 279A. The notification for bringing into force Article 279A with effect from 12th September, 2016 was issued on 10th September, 2016.

As per Article 279A of the amended Constitution, the GST Council which will be a joint forum of the Centre and the States, shall consist of the following members: -

- Union Finance Minister – Chairperson
- The Union Minister of State, in-charge of Revenue of finance - Member
- The Minister In-charge of finance or taxation or any other Minister nominated by each State Government - Members

As per Article 279A (4), the Council will make recommendations to the Union and the States on important issues related to GST, like the goods and services that may be subjected or exempted from GST, model GST Laws, principles that govern Place of Supply, threshold limits, GST rates including the floor rates with bands, special rates for raising additional resources during natural calamities/disasters, special provisions for certain States, etc.

Creation of the GST Council

The Union Cabinet approved setting up of GST Council on 12th September, 2016 and also setting up its Secretariat as per the following details:

- Creation of the GST Council as per Article 279A of the amended Constitution;
- Creation of the GST Council Secretariat, with its office at New Delhi;
- Appointment of the Secretary (Revenue) as the Ex-officio Secretary to the GST Council;
- Inclusion of the Chairperson, Central Board of Excise and Customs (CBEC), as a permanent invitee (non-voting) to all proceedings of the GST Council;
- Create one post of Additional Secretary to the GST Council in the GST Council Secretariat (at the level of Additional Secretary to the Government of India), and four posts of Commissioner in the GST Council Secretariat

(at the level of Joint Secretary to the Government of India). The Cabinet also decided to provide for adequate funds for meeting the recurring and non-recurring expenses of the GST Council Secretariat, the entire cost for which shall be borne by the Central Government. The GST Council Secretariat shall be manned by officers taken on deputation from both the Central and State Governments.

GST Council - Constitution

- Consists of Finance Minister, the MOS (Finance) and the Minister of Finance / Taxation of each State
- Chairperson – Union FM
- Vice Chairperson - to be chosen amongst the Ministers of State Government
- Quorum is 50% of total members
- Decision by 75% majority
- Council to make recommendations on everything related to GST including laws, rules and rates etc.

GST Council Functions

They are mention in Article 279(4) of the Constitution. It will make recommendations on important issues related to GST, like

- Goods and Services that may be subjected or exempted from GST.
- Model GST Laws.
- Principles that govern Place of Supply, threshold limits, GST rates.
- GST rates will including the floor rates with bands
- Special rates for raising additional resources during natural disasters/ calamities, special provisions for certain States, etc.

GST Council Meetings

GST Council has met seventeen times since its constitution and some important decisions taken in the GST Council meeting are:-

- Rules for conduct of business in GST Council.
 - Timetable for implementation of GST.
 - The threshold limit for exemption from levy of GST would be Rs. 20 lakhs for the States except for the Special Category States, as enumerated in Article 279A of the Constitution, for which it will be Rs 10 Lakhs).
 - The threshold for availing the Composition scheme would be Rs. 75 lakhs in States other than the North East States, Sikkim and Himachal Pradesh where the threshold for availing the Composition scheme would be Rs. 50 lakhs. The GST Council has also recommended that manufacturers of the following goods shall not be eligible for the Composition Levy; Ice cream and other edible ice, whether or not containing cocoa, Pan masala, Tobacco and manufactured tobacco substitutes. Service providers would be kept out of the Composition Scheme, except restaurant services.
 - To compensate States for 5 years for loss of revenue due to implementation of GST, the base year for the revenue of the State would be 2015-16 and a fixed growth rate of 14% will be applied to it.
 - Approval of the Draft GST Rules on registration, payment, return, refund and invoice, valuation, input tax credit, composition and transitional provisions.
 - All entities exempted from payment of indirect tax under any existing tax incentive scheme would pay tax in the GST regime and the decision to continue with any incentive scheme shall be with the concerned State or Central government. In case, the State or Central Government decides to continue with any existing exemption/incentive scheme; it will be administered by way of a reimbursement mechanism.
 - Adoption of four slabs tax rate structure of 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. In addition, there would be a category of exempt goods and further a cess would be levied on certain goods such as luxury cars, aerated drinks, pan masala and tobacco products, over and above the rate of 28% for payment of compensation to the states.
 - GST rates on 1211 items were approved at the 14th GST Council meeting held at Srinagar on 18th and 19th of May 2017.
 - At the 15th GST Council meeting held at New Delhi on 3rd June 2017, tax rates on the remaining goods were approved.
 - 28 states, and 2 Union Territories with Legislatures (Delhi and Puducherry) have already passed their respective State GST Bill in their State Assemblies.
 - Issue of cross empowerment and administrative division of taxpayers between the States and Centre has been resolved.
- The Central Goods and Services Tax bill, Integrated Goods and Services Tax bill, Union Territories (without legislature) Goods and Services Tax bill and Goods and Services Tax (Compensation to States) bill have been passed by the Lok Sabha on 29.03.2017 and by the Rajya Sabha on 06.04.2017.

Exemption Issue

- Threshold for exemption for businesses in Northeastern and hill states will be for annual turnover below Rs.10 lakh and rest of India it will below Rs.20 lakh.
- The Northeastern and hill states have been accorded special status by the Constitutional Amendment paving the way for the GST.

Administrative Control Issue

- Consensus was reached on the contentious issue of administrative control over indirect tax assesses.

- States will have sole jurisdiction over assesseees having a turnover of Rs.1.5 crore or less. In case turnover exceeding that limit, the administrative control will be jointly with the central and state governments.
- The existing 11 lakh service tax assesses will continue to be under the jurisdiction of the Centre.
- Revenue officials in the States will be trained for assessing assesses in the services sector as GST allows states to also tax services

Compensation formula

The compensation that Central Government will pay to states for losses of revenue because of the transition to GST regime will be routinely, quarterly or bi-monthly.

Base Year

The GST Council also agreed to settle 2015-16 as the base year for calculating the compensation.

GST (Goods and Services Tax) and Co-Operative Federalism

It all began with the Centre and States agreeing to have concurrent power to tax goods and services. The Centre let go of its exclusive power to tax manufacture of goods (i.e. Excise) and provision of services (i.e. Service Tax), and the States gave up their exclusive power to tax sale of goods (sales tax / VAT). Both the Center and the States agreed to share their powers to achieve uniformity and remove compartmentalization in indirect taxation.

Different rates of VAT in States coupled with non-vat table CST (Central Sales Tax) and broken input tax credit chain in inter-state transactions resulted in tax on tax (cascading of taxes) leading to multiple tax zones within India. Now under GST, the same tax rates will be levied on a particular item on its supply concurrently both by the Center and State, thereby bringing

uniformity in tax. GST will subsume a number of existing indirect taxes being levied independently by the Centre and State Governments. These include Central Excise duty, Service Tax, VAT, Purchase Tax, Central Sales Tax, Entry Tax, Local Body Taxes, Luxury Tax, etc. Such a long list of taxes with requirements of filing returns and carrying out tedious multiple calculations, all replaced by one tax with a nationwide common rate on particular items, isn't it wonderful the way Center and States came together to evolve and adopt the new system?

The spirit of co-operative federalism has thus helped remove compartmentalization of powers to tax. The Constitution of India has also been amended accordingly. This fundamental reordering of federal fiscal relations for the cause of common good shows the strength and resolve of the federal structure.

This convergence for the cause of larger public good has been made possible, initially due to the mechanism of the Empowered Committee of Ministers (EC) and later the GST Council. Under the GST regime, the Centre & States will act on the recommendations of the GST Council. GST Council comprises of the Union Finance Minister, Union Minister of State for Finance and all Finance Ministers of the States. 2/3rd of Voting power is with the States and 1/3rd with the Centre which reflects the accommodative spirit of federalism. Consensus among st members has been the guiding principle for taking decisions in GST Council in all its decisions leading up to GST's launch on 1st July 2017, though the Constitution provides for decisions being taken by a 3/4th majority of members present and voting. The very fact that there has been no need to resort to voting to take any decisions taken till now in 18 meetings held so far reflects the spirit of "One Nation, One Aspiration, One Determination".

The participation of all States and Center in the framing of GST laws has led to the following features in the GST Laws:

Harmonization of GST laws across the country

Even though Centre and each State legislature (except Jammu & Kashmir, where it is under process) have passed their own GST Acts, they are all based on the Model GST law drafted jointly by the Centre & the States. Consequently, all the laws have virtually identical provisions.

Common Definitions

There are common definitions in the GST Act.

Common Procedures/Formats

There are common procedures; common formats in all laws, even the sections and subsections in CGST Act and SGST Act are same. UTGST Act provides that most of the provisions in CGST Act, as stated in Section 21 shall apply to UTGST Act also.

Common Compliance Mechanism

GSTN, a not-for-profit, non-government company promoted jointly by the Central and State Governments, is the common compliance portal and the taxpayers shall interface with all states as well as Center through this portal.

Other significant areas, where such co-operation has been displayed by the Center and States are as under:

Joint Capacity Building Efforts:

Joint Capacity Building efforts by Center as well as all the States are being organized wherein for the first time the training of officers of Center and State is being conducted under the auspices of National Academy of Customs, Indirect Taxes and Narcotics (NACIN). NACIN has formed a Joint Coordination Committee in each State comprising of Center, State and NACIN Officers for overseeing Capacity Building efforts.

Joint Trade Awareness & Outreach Efforts:

Center along with the State Government Officials has been organizing Joint Trade Awareness & Outreach programs wherein for the first time the Officers came together to create GST awareness amongst Trade and other stakeholders.

Cross Empowerment of Officers of Center as well as States:

Though GST will be jointly administered by Center and State, for ensuring ease of doing business, but the individual taxpayer will have a single interface with only one Tax Authority either Center or State. In order to encourage cooperation and harmonize the decisions under both the Acts, the officers appointed under the SGST Act or the UGST Act shall be authorized to be the proper officer for the purposes of CGST Act and vice versa.

Joint Implementation Committees

In order to ensure smooth roll out of GST, the GST Council has formed a three tier structure consisting of : the Office of the Revenue Secretary, a GST Implementation Committee and eight (8) Standing Committees. In addition, eighteen (18) Sectoral Groups representing various sectors of the economy have been set up. All these Committees viz. GST Implementation Committee (GIC), Standing Committees and Sectoral Groups have representation of Center and State Officers in the spirit of cooperative federalism to ensure quick administrative decisions required before and after the roll out and ensure effective coordination for smooth implementation of GST.

II. CONCLUSION

Goods and Services Tax (GST) was based on the concept of pooled sovereignty and cooperative federalism. GST intends to transform India into a true economic union, with the aim of 'One Nation, One Tax, One Market'. The free movement of goods and services will give fillip to employment opportunities and give consumers a

wider choice and better prices. This economic integration will not only boost economic growth, but also bind the nation better. It is an idea whose time has come and would not have materialized but for the spirit of co-operation displayed by the Center and the States. Indeed, GST in India in its conception, enactment and implementation is an example of real 'co-operative federalism' at work, in tune with the unique character of India – 'Unity in Diversity'.